

Modeling Citations and Cartels

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Abstract. Citation data are widely used by researchers and administrators. Interpreting the results of citation analyses, however, is non-trivial on account of the uncertainty around motivations for citation, varied disciplinary practices, data quality, and the lack of ground truths. *In-silico* approaches that harness autonomous behavior and randomness offer an option in this regard. We have developed an agent-based model of citation dynamics that generates synthetic networks where articles are represented by nodes and citations by edges. We characterize the model through baseline simulations, sensitivity, and ablation analysis. We also model the behavior of cartels that seek to manipulate citations. We observe that fitness (epistemic quality) is a principal driver of citations and that cartel membership does not lend itself to elite performance.

Keywords: agent-based models, network analysis, citation cartels

1 Introduction

Citation data enjoy widespread use by experts and non-experts, and are used to study productivity, impact, collaboration, community structure, and misconduct among other topics of inquiry [17, 6, 4, 39, 12, 29]. Interpreting citation studies is challenging given the uncertainty around motivations for citation, subjective views on what ought to be cited, disciplinary norms, data quality and incommensurability between studies. While a unifying theory of citation [38] that explains citation behavior is not evident, a patchwork of historical theories of citation is extant that can be roughly grouped into normative and rhetorical categories [23, 10, 18, 9, 33, 20]. Although individually plausible, none of these theories is well-supported by experimental results at scale; likely because of the challenge in quantifying and distinguishing between overlapping motivations imputed to researchers.

From a different perspective, mathematical models of citation [31, 14] that incorporate randomness and determinism offer explanatory promise. Simulations using agent-based models (ABMs) [13, 36, 15, 2, 8] that leverage autonomous behavior in addition to randomness represent a complementary avenue for model-based reasoning and discovery. Herein, we present the Scalable Agent-based Simulator for Citation Analysis with Sampling and Authors (SASCA-ReSA) [25], an ABM that parsimoniously models the growth of citation networks. SASCA-ReSA

is the latest in a series of citation models we have previously developed, PyABM, SASCA, and SASCA-ReS [8, 24, 27], and is more complex than its predecessors.

In SASCA-ReSA, the input to a simulation is a citation network—represented as a directed graph with articles as nodes and citations as edges. The output of a simulation is a larger citation network created through the addition of new nodes in time-steps of a year. Notable in SASCA-ReSA is the addition of *author attributes* in the form of a corresponding author who may contribute multiple articles to the network and a count of authors for each article. These new features enable modeling author reputation and scale of collaboration as factors influencing citation counts.

Nodes in SASCA-ReSA networks are of two types, seeds and agents. The input network consists of seed nodes, which do not make citations but can be cited. Agents are created during a simulation and can both make citations to seed nodes and agents, and also can be cited by other agents. Thus, each *new* node added to the growing network is an autonomous agent that makes citations to other nodes. The number of nodes added in each time-step and the duration of the simulation is specified by a user.

Both types of nodes have *attributes* that attract citations from agents. The attributes of a node are its year of publication, its fitness (a measure of its intrinsic quality), *in_degree* (count of citations received), *out_degree* (citation quota), the reputation of its corresponding author (*ar*), and the count of authors (*na*) contributing to it. Fitness is assigned to each node by sampling from a power-law distribution ranging from 1:1000, *na*, the count of authors contributing to each article, is assigned through sampling from a real-world distribution, and *ar* is defined as the H-index [16], computed (in-network) for an author. *In_degree* and *ar* are updated at each time step, which is set to a year by default.

Additionally, each agent is assigned a quota of citations to make and a ‘*phenotype*’ that influences their choice of nodes to cite. Based on their phenotype, agents score eligible nodes (Methods) and make weighted random selections to satisfy their citation quotas. Once an agent completes its quota of citations, it remains a part of the network and can receive citations from other agents throughout the simulation. An agent’s phenotype consists of weights that sum to 1 for *in_degree* (*pa_w*), fitness (*fit_w*), author reputation (*ar_w*), and author count (*na_w*). Additionally, an agent’s affinity for target proximity to itself in the network is specified by a parameter α , and recency, the propensity of authors to cite recent papers, is enforced through a separate protocol described in [27].

At the network level, the distribution of articles per author fits a Lotkas’s Law distribution [22]. Further details of SASCA-ReSA are provided in Methods and a Github site [25], where the software implementation of the model is archived as open source.

SASCA-ReSA enables the study of strategies of individual researchers as well as the effects of these strategies on network structure. In the following sections, we largely focus on the former, which is framed as optimizing citations made (references) in order maximize citations received. We first examine the model using a one factor at a time (OFAT) approach [5]. Next, we examine the effect

of planting a small number of agents with defined attributes and phenotype into a simulation followed by an ablation study. Finally, we use SASCA-ReSA in a simple representation of the behavior of citation cartels [12, 19]. In this work, we use agent-based modeling to stimulate thought and reasoning and do not claim identical citation behavior in the real-world. We do not explore the question of whether evaluating research through citation analysis is judicious (our view is that it is not) nor do we support ‘gaming the metrics’ [3] in any shape or form.

2 Results

2.1 Baseline Observations

SASCA-ReSA was used to generate baseline data using a *standard* protocol [8] originating from the development of SASCA-ReSA and its precursors. In this protocol, a seed network is allowed to grow by 3% each year for 30 years through the iterative addition of agents. The seed network [8] is derived from a citation network centered around the cell biology literature concerning extracellular vesicles [35] but can be replaced, in a simulation, by any other citation network or random directed graph. The final network consists of 1,193,102 nodes (491,532 seed nodes and 701,570 agents). During these baseline experiments, the agent background was *randomized*, that is, agent phenotypes were randomized with respect to `pa_w`, `fit_w`, `ar_w`, and `na_w` (all four summing to 1 for each agent), while fitness, α , and `out_degree` were assigned to each agent through sampling from synthetic or real-world distributions (Methods). In a variant of this protocol termed *static*, combinations of attributes and phenotype weights were fixed for all agents as described.

Table 1. Distributional statistics (quantiles) of agent in-degree across 10 baseline replicates (701,570 agents per replicate) using a standard protocol. The median (q0.5) is stable across replicates (SD = 0.0) while variability increases at the extreme tail, with the maximum in-degree varying by $\pm 12,397$ (rounded) across replicates.

Statistic	Mean	SD
q0.5	12.0	0.0
q0.75	27.6	0.5
q0.90	59.0	0.5
q0.99	301.4	3.5
q0.999	1,706.5	46.8
q0.9999	8,987.1	424.9
max	72,280.7	12,396.8

We note consistency across standard simulations with a sharp increase in variability after the 99th percentile of `in_degree` (Table 1). To explore correlations between attributes and phenotypes with citations accumulated, we computed the

Fig. 1. Baseline data from 10 simulations with randomized agents. (i) Left panel: In-degree distribution. Roughly 7.03% (SD=0.037%) of agents received zero citations and are excluded from the plot (ii) Right panel: Spearman’s rank correlation of agent attributes with final in-degree. Error bars shown are +/- SD.

Spearman correlation coefficient [34] (Fig. 1). The citation count accumulated by agents correlated most strongly with publication year, which is logical since the earlier an agent is created the more time-steps it can receive citations in. The next strongest correlation with citation count was out_degree or count of references made by an agent, which is also consistent with results from our preceding models of citation. Progressively weaker correlations were seen with respect to the number of authors, initial author reputation, fitness and α .

We also examined the median values of the publication year, fitness, number of authors, initial ar_w , and α (Fig. 2). In this experiment, agents were grouped into tiers consisting of all agents, the top 1%, 0.1%, and 0.01% by in-degree and pooled across 10 baseline replicates to consider 7,015,700 agent-observations. Citation counts corresponding to publication year decrease monotonically toward the extreme tail, reflecting an advantage for agents that are created early. Fitness increases with in-degree tier, rising from a median of 1 for all agents to 27 at the top 0.01%, a trend that is again consistent with observations from previous models [8, 27, 24]. Interestingly, initial ar shows a non-monotonic pattern, peaking at the top 1% (median 7) before declining at higher thresholds, which may suggest that, at the extreme tail, fitness and early publication are stronger determinants of in_degree than author reputation. α is more or less invariant across tiers, consistent with its weak correlation.

OFAT Analysis To examine the effects of individual variables on citations received by agents, we designed static conditions in which either a single attribute or phenotype weight of an agent was increased to near the maximum possible value while the remaining attributes and weights were held relatively constant (Table 2).

We measured baseline data with either randomized or static agent backgrounds. For the static background, agent weights for preferential attachment (pa), fitness, num_authors (na), and author_reputation (ar) were set to 0.25

Publication year	2001	1994	1993	1990
Fitness	1	2	12	27
Out-degree	35	61	66	74
Number of authors	6	8	9	9
Initial author reputation	2	7	3	2
Alpha	0.500	0.547	0.531	0.493
	All agents	Top 1%	Top 0.1%	Top 0.01%

Fig. 2. Agent attributes by tiered in-degree. Median values of six agent attributes — publication year, fitness, out_degree, number of authors, initial author reputation (*iar*), and α — computed for all agents and for the top 1%, 0.1%, and 0.01% of agents by in_degree, pooled across 10 baseline replicates. Each row is independently normalized to its own range. Publication year decreases monotonically toward the extreme tail, reflecting the temporal accumulation of citations. Fitness increases with in-degree tier, rising from a median of 1 for all agents to 27 at the top 0.01%. Out_degree increases monotonically from 35 to 74 across tiers, consistent with its role as the second strongest correlate of in-degree. Initial *ar* shows a non-monotonic pattern, peaking at the top 1% (median 7) before declining at higher thresholds, suggesting that at the extreme tail fitness and early publication may be stronger determinants of citation counts than author reputation. α varies very little across tiers and is technically a phenotypic parameter.

each. Three replicates were conducted for each condition and each condition was applied to all agents in the simulation.

For attributes, the effect of either high out_degree (249) or high α (0.95) was studied in randomized and static agent backgrounds. We did not perform an OFAT for fitness, since setting all agents to an equally high fitness is not interpretable. However, the influence of fitness is examined in the ablation experiment described in a following section.

When studying the impact of sharply increasing one element of agent phenotype (Table 2), each weight was set to 0.91 while the remaining weights were assigned 0.03. For example W1, the preferential attachment (PA) dominant condition, has the weight for preferential attachment set to 0.91 and the weights for fitness, author count, and initial author reputation set to 0.03 each.

The results show very little difference between random and static baseline configurations except at higher percentile values. While we report the maximum in_degree achieved, we consider it less reliable than the 99.9th or 99.99th percentile since peak values can vary significantly between replicates of the same experiment. For example, for the baseline data summarized in Table 1, the maximum ranges from 54,438 to 94,147 across 10 replicates — a range of nearly

Table 2. OFAT experiment: in-degree distributional statistics across 11 conditions (701,570 agents per replicate, 3 replicates per condition, with statistics pooled across replicates). BSL_rand and BSL_stat are baseline conditions with phenotype weights either randomized or set to 0.25 respectively. W1–W4 are weight conditions in which one citation weight is set to 0.91 and the remaining three to 0.03. W5a and W5b fix out_degree at 249 for all agents with equal or randomized weights respectively; W6a and W6b fix α at 0.95 with either equal or randomized weights. The top 0.1% and top 0.01% thresholds are defined relative to the baseline in-degree distribution ($\geq 1,699$ and $\geq 9,124$ citations respectively).

Rx	median	mean	p99.9	p99.99	max
baseline conditions					
BSL_rand	12	33.1	1,699	9,124	100,883
BSL_stat	12	33.0	1,717	8,901	79,011
weight conditions					
W1 pa_wt dominant	10	32.9	2,469	18,064	146,764
W2 fit_w dominant	12	33.6	2,263	12,471	170,058
W3 na_w dominant	12	32.8	1,596	8,193	128,514
W4 ar_w dominant	9	32.6	1,624	4,548	24,660
high out_degree (249)					
W5a Equal weights (0.25)	68	191.6	9,332	63,017	459,428
W5b randomized weights	68	192.3	9,367	62,479	438,259
high α (0.95)					
W6a Equal weights (0.25)	14	32.5	1,333	6,329	41,392
W6b randomized weights	14	32.5	1,300	6,501	53,430

40,000 with a standard deviation (SD) of 11,761. In contrast, the SD at the 99.9th percentile is roughly 44.

Among the weight conditions, W1, the *pa_w* dominant condition, has the heaviest tail at the 99.9th percentile (2,469), where a small number of papers accumulate extreme citation counts while the median citation count drops slightly. W2, the *fit_w* dominant condition, is slightly less heavy-tailed than W1 with the top 0.1% also at 0.14 suggesting that in a *fit_w* dominant environment, the best articles are well cited. W3, the author count weight (*na_w*) dominant condition, exhibits mild compression below baseline suggesting that the number of authors on a paper does not concentrate citations very effectively or frequently. W4, the author reputation weight (*ar_w*) dominant condition, is the most compressed, with p99.9 of 1,624 and p99.99 of 4,548 which we interpret as an indication of limits to the effect of author reputation.

The W5 experiment shows a dramatic increase in citations, which is to be expected since the total number of citations being made is much higher than the other conditions although it is also clear that these citations are not evenly distributed. The W6 experiment, high α condition, shows citations slightly below baseline at p99.9 (1,300-1,333), indicating a mild compression effect of high α .

The W5 and W6 experiments are consistent with our earlier findings [8] and prior observations on ‘high-referencing’ and fractional counting [32, 21].

We infer from the OFAT experiment that `out_degree` is the most influential factor in terms of driving citations in our model system. Among the weight conditions, `pa_w` and `fit_w` amplify the heavy tail seen in baseline runs while `na_w` and `ar_w` suppress it. However, these effect sizes are modest. High α mildly compresses the distribution. Thus, prolific citing is a major driver of counts with citation preferences playing a secondary role in shaping the tail but not the bulk of the distribution. Note, however, that fitness is not examined in the OFAT experiment.

2.2 Planted Nodes

A logical follow-up question is whether a small number of agents with specific attributes can accumulate disproportionate citations in the background of a randomized environment. We attempt to explore this question below using planted nodes. We examined the effect of planting a small number of agents of fixed phenotype in the larger randomized background. This experiment was performed in two ways: either simultaneously planting 5 agents in year 1 of the simulation (P5) or a staggered planting of one agent in each of the first 5 years of the simulation (PS5). A reference phenotype with high `out_degree`, high fitness, and a high number of authors derived from data generated during development, was used for comparison (Table 3).

Table 3. Fixed phenotype parameters for planted nodes in P5 and PS5 experiments. Planted nodes are assigned fixed values for fitness, `num_authors`, and `out_degree`. Phenotype weights sum to 1.0 in all conditions. The reference phenotype serves as a comparison for the fitness-dominant and social-dominant strategies. Fitness tiers: f1 = 1–10, f2 = 10–100, f3 = 100–1000.

	<code>out_degree</code>	fitness	<code>num_authors</code>	<code>out_degree</code>	<code>pa_w</code>	<code>fit_w</code>	<code>na_w</code>	<code>ar_w</code>	α	tier
reference	unrestr.	200	100	249	0.25	0.20	0.35	0.20	0.5	f3
fitness-dom.	restr.	200	6	35	0.20	0.65	0.10	0.05	0.5	f3
fitness-dom.	unrestr.	200	6	249	0.25	0.55	0.15	0.05	0.5	f3
social-dom.	restr.	5	1,000	35	0.20	0.10	0.60	0.10	0.5	f1
social-dom.	unrestr.	5	1,000	249	0.20	0.10	0.60	0.10	0.5	f1

Two scenarios were explored: a fitness-dominant scenario in which fitness was set high and the number of authors was low and a social-dominant scenario in which fitness was low and the number of authors was high. In each case, `out_degree` was either set to 249 (unrestricted) or 35 (restricted). Three replicates were conducted for each experiment for both the P5 and PS5 series of experiments. Pooled results are shown in Fig. 3 and Table 4, which suggest that PS5 outperforms P5 at the median (four of five conditions) and at the extreme

Fig. 3. Comparison of simultaneous (P5) and staggered (PS5) planting strategies across five conditions. Each panel shows a metric of citation performance for 75 planted nodes (5 conditions \times 5 nodes \times 3 replicates), with values pooled across 3 replicates per condition, under simultaneous entry in year 1 (P5, blue) and staggered entry across years 1–5 (PS5, orange). From left to right: median in-degree, percentage of planted nodes exceeding the baseline top 0.1% threshold ($\geq 1,707$ citations), and percentage exceeding the baseline top 0.01% threshold ($\geq 9,018$ citations). PS5 outperforms P5 in the majority of conditions and metrics, with the largest gains in the fitness-dominant unrestricted and reference conditions. Restricted conditions (out_degree=35) show more modest and variable gains from staggering. The reference condition achieves 100% of planted nodes above both thresholds under PS5.

tail (three of five conditions). Interestingly, the reference phenotype is the best performer in both series.

Fitness-dominant unrestricted is a close second, which suggests that high fitness combined with high out_degree favors success in a randomized background. A contrast between the restricted (od=35) vs unrestricted (od=249) is evident and restricted conditions mostly perform worse than their unrestricted counterparts. Social-dominant conditions show a less consistent pattern with respect to fitness-dominant conditions throughout, suggesting that a social-dominant strategy may be less reliable. The temporal effect of the PS5 experiments is non-monotonic and may reflect stochastic effects.

While the reference phenotype outcompetes the more formally designed ones, the findings in both cases are consistent with each other. In summary, fitness and out_degree are the two most influential attributes for a planted node and staggered entry (PS5) outperforms simultaneous planting (P5).

2.3 Ablation Analysis

Since the reference phenotype performed the best in the planted node experiments, we used it in an ablation experiment to infer the relative contributions of attributes and weights to citation counts achieved under both P5 and PS5 designs.

The ablation analysis was designed as follows. Following the design of the planted node experiment five nodes are planted according to the P5 or PS5

Table 4. Planted node experiment results for simultaneous (P5) and staggered (PS5) entry strategies across five conditions (5 planted nodes per condition per replicate, 3 replicates per condition, 15 planted nodes per condition total). Median in-degree, percentage of planted nodes exceeding the baseline top 0.1% threshold ($\geq 1,707$ citations) and top 0.01% threshold ($\geq 9,018$ citations), and number of rank-1 finishes across 3 replicates. P5 nodes are planted simultaneously in year 1 and PS5 nodes are planted in staggered fashion, years 1–5. Values are pooled across 3 replicates.

Rx	P5 (simultaneous)				PS5 (staggered)			
	median	Top 0.1%	Top 0.01%	Rank 1	median	Top 0.1%	Top 0.01%	Rank 1
fit-dom restr.	12,044	93%	53%	0	7,517	93%	47%	0
fit-dom unrestr.	32,774	100%	73%	1	56,297	100%	87%	3
reference	39,265	100%	80%	3	59,753	100%	100%	3
soc-dom restr.	9,661	80%	53%	0	12,321	93%	53%	0
soc-dom unrestr.	8,968	100%	47%	1	21,557	100%	67%	1

protocols. Three replicates were performed for each condition (15 planted nodes per condition). Ablation was grouped into two tiers.

Tier 1 ablations (A1–A4) target phenotype and consist of setting one weight to zero and redistributing its value proportionally across the weight settings of the reference phenotype. A1–A4 ablate `pa_wt`, `fit_wt`, `n_wt`, and `ar_wt` respectively.

Of these, A4 (remove `ar` weight) is the best-performing condition in both P5 and PS5, with PS5 median reaching 65,672 and 100% of nodes in the top 0.01%. We propose that without ablation, the `ar` weight in the reference phenotype could divert citation preference away from fitness and `num_authors`, suppressing performance. This is consistent with the OFAT finding that AR-dominant conditions produce the most compressed distributions.

Removing other weights has little effect. A1 (remove `pa_w`), A2 (remove `fit_w`), and A3 (remove `na_w`) all perform comparably to or better than A0 in both strategies, suggesting that attributes are more influential than individual weights and that reference weight configuration could be further optimized. `Num_authors` as an attribute is non-critical when fitness is high. A6 (`num_authors` ablated to 6) performs well with 100% of its planted nodes in the top 0.1% 100% — confirming that fitness and `out_degree` together are sufficient for high citation accumulation regardless of team size. The PS5 series generally outperforms P5 across ablation conditions, consistent with the planting experiments. A5 and A6 are very similar between strategies, suggesting that staggering provides less benefit when a key attribute is ablated. In A7, `out_degree=35` is the empirical median rather than the empirical floor value of 10, so A7 may understate the importance of `out_degree`.

Tier 2 ablations (A5–A7) set one node attribute to a neutral value (median of the distribution) while holding weights fixed (Fig. 4). A5–A7 ablate fitness, the number of authors (`na`) and `out_degree` (`od`) respectively. Fitness and `out_degree` emerge as the two critical attributes. A5 (fitness ablated to 1) and A7 (`out_degree`

Fig. 4. Ablation experiment results for simultaneous (P5) and staggered (PS5) planting strategies across eight conditions. Each panel shows a metric of citation performance for planted nodes under the reference phenotype with one attribute or weight ablated at a time (15 planted nodes per condition, averaged across 3 replicates). From left to right: median in-degree, percentage of planted nodes exceeding the baseline top 0.1% threshold ($\geq 1,707$ citations), and percentage exceeding the baseline top 0.01% threshold ($\geq 9,018$ citations). P5 nodes are planted simultaneously in year 1 (blue); PS5 nodes are planted in staggered years 1–5 (orange). A5 (ablate fitness, fitness=1) and A7 (ablate out_degree, out_degree=35) produce the largest performance drops across all metrics, identifying fitness and out_degree as the two load-bearing attributes of the reference phenotype. PS5 generally outperforms P5, consistent with the planting experiment results.

reduced to 35) produce the largest in_degree drops across all metrics in both P5 and PS5. In PS5, the median drops from 33,137 (reference) to 3,546 for A5 and 17,013 for A7.

2.4 Modeling Citation Cartels

The planted node strategy can be extended to the case of citation cartels. However, studying citation cartels can be challenging on account of benign citation behavior that may generate cartel-like patterns of citation. In an ABM environment, however, it is possible to construct agents with explicitly designed behaviors that model cartels [30]. We assume the existence of a group of researchers who collude to cite each other’s work in order to boost their citation counts for mutual benefit. Additional assumptions are that members of this group do not enjoy strong author reputations and that each cartel member publishes at a uniform rate of one article per year. Thus, each cartel member publishes multiple articles and those articles act as agents when making citations according to the rule set conferred upon them. Note that we use the term *cartel member* to refer to authors who are in a cartel, *cartel agent* to refer to articles published by these members, and *background agent* to identify any agent whose corresponding author is not in a cartel.

The initial design consists of planting a single cartel within our standard simulation. In the interest of parsimony, we do not consider incentives around

Fig. 5. Cartel agents at elite levels of performance. Articles published by cartel authors (*cartel-r* and *cartel-p*) underperform compared to a control group. The figure shows the fraction of cartel articles in the top 1% of agents by *in_degree* relative to the expected value (horizontal dotted line) for six different cartel sizes.

peer-review, journal reputation, researcher affiliations, or prior collaborations, which can also be targets of collusive activity [3, 28]. Articles published by cartel members are assigned a fitness of 1 to reflect minimum quality and the number of authors of each cartel agent was set to 6. Finally, each cartel agent directs 50% of its citation quota to articles by other cartel members. To select the members of a cartel we first annotated the seed set publications with author IDs and then randomly selected a group of authors, matching the size of the cartel, whose first publication was in the last 2 years.

Three counterfactual scenarios are represented in the design: *cartel-p* where cartel agents use 50% of their quota to cite other cartel agents based on attributes and phenotype, *cartel-r* where cartel agents spend 50% of their quota by randomly citing articles by other cartel members, and *ctrl* where cartel agents behave indistinguishably from background agents in the simulation. In all three scenarios, cartel members publish at the same rate. Of note is that while *cartel-r* and *cartel-p* agents are generated by other cartel agents, *ctrl*-agents are created with randomly selected generator nodes (as in the case of background nodes).

Cartels were varied in size from 5, 25, 125, 250, 500, and 1000. Experiments were run under either of two settings: *restrictive* where cartel agents had fitness = 1, *num_authors* = 6, *out_degree* = 35, *alpha* = 0.5, and phenotype weights of 0.25 each, and *relaxed* where cartel members had fitness = 1 and *num_authors* = 6, but phenotype weights, *out_degree*, and *alpha* were randomized as for background agents.

Seed nodes were excluded from analysis of cartel simulations. We first examined the representation of cartel agents in the top 1% of all agents by *in_degree* (Fig. 5), which shows that *cartel-r* and *cartel-p* members perform worse than the control group under the conditions tested with respect to the fraction of their agents in the top 1% of agents by *in_degree*. In this experiment, relaxed conditions outperformed restricted conditions. Interestingly, a size-dependent effect is seen with cartels of size 125 and 250 performing better than other sizes

Fig. 6. Cartel authors have an initial advantage in terms of *annual citations* received that decreases over time and as cartel size increases. The figure shows average citations received per cartel author per year during a 30-year simulation in a randomized agent background. Counterfactual scenarios: (i) *ctrl*; agents (articles) of cartel members cite identical to background agents, (ii) *cartel-r*; cartel members cite each other randomly, and (iii) *cartel-p*; cartel members cite each other based on attributes and phenotype. For *cartel-r* and *cartel-p* scenarios, at most 50% of the citations made a cartel agent are made to cartel members and the remaining to nodes outside the cartel according to attribute and phenotype as in *ctrl*. The figure is constructed from 108 independent simulations that generated roughly 76M agent observations.

tested. We speculate that this may be due to a combination of sampling and competition effects although further study is clearly necessary for elucidation.

Next, we examined the kinetics of citation accumulation for cartel members over the thirty year simulation period (Fig 6 and Fig. 7). The annual rate of the control group increases rapidly and exceeds the cartel group roughly after the 15 year point for larger cartel sizes. In terms of cumulative citations, however, the *cartel-r* and *cartel-p* groups exceed the control group at many cartel sizes. The cumulative advantage for cartel is most consistent under relaxed conditions and the control group does win under restrictive conditions for intermediate size cartels. These stylized experiments suggest that cartels have a cumulative advantage that does not extend to elite performance but membership still confers an advantage at non-elite levels. However, this advantage is at the expense of non-members in our simulations, which may reflect a similar pattern in the real world. The data also suggest that the size of the cartel matters in that larger cartels have a greater cumulative advantage. These findings are consistent with Secchi’s preceding study using a simpler agent-based model at a smaller scale [30].

Fig. 7. Cartel authors have a sustained advantage in terms of *cumulative citations* received. Counterfactual scenarios: (i) *ctrl*; agents (articles) of cartel members cite identical to background agents, (ii) *cartel-r*; cartel members cite each other randomly, and (iii) *cartel-p*; cartel members cite each other based on attributes and phenotype. For cartel-r and cartel-p scenarios, at most 50% of the citations made a cartel agent are made to cartel members and the remaining to nodes outside the cartel according to attribute and phenotype as in ctrl. Each data point is the mean of citations per cartel author across 3 replicates. The figure is constructed from 108 independent simulations that generated roughly 76M agent observations.

Finally, to examine community structure associated with cartel behavior, we performed community search experiments (Fig. 8), using our implementation [37] of a method based on k -cores [11]. A k -core is a maximal connected set of nodes where every node is adjacent to at least k other nodes in the set; hence the “coreness” of a set of nodes is the largest k so that the set is a k -core. In this method, which is distinct from partitioning the entire network into clusters, the input is a set A of nodes and the output is a set B of nodes such that $A \subseteq B$ and B is a k -core with the largest possible k . The query set A in this case is the set of cartel agents.

Applying this technique to the control group, we obtained extremely large (all above 1 million nodes) and sparse communities ($k \leq 3$). In contrast, the cartel-p or cartel-r group produced smaller and denser sets of nodes, with density decreasing as cartel size increased. The cartel-p group exhibited slightly denser groups than the cartel-r group as cartel size increased. These results testify to mostly limited advantage to cartel behavior.

Fig. 8. Articles by members of small cartels form dense community structures. A k -core based community search was performed using the set of cartel agents as query nodes.

3 Discussion

From a method development standpoint, ABMs are especially useful for exploring citation dynamics since it is possible to simulate under controlled conditions using an idealized model in an artificial environment. This abstraction comes with a penalty in terms of reflecting reality. For example, our SASCA-ReSA studies do not capture the interpersonal interactions that are integral to research communities. Defining an optimal balance between idealism and realism is a subjective choice further constrained by the cost of computing. A future version of our citation model will incorporate some aspect of affinity between authors though.

The principal lessons learned from SASCA-ReSA, and earlier models in its lineage, is that fitness, out_degree, and of an agent are the major drivers of the citations it accumulates. Agents created early in a simulation have the advantage of being eligible as targets for a greater period of time. Author reputation (ar) has a more nuanced effect. Extrapolating our observations on fitness to the real world presents a challenge that we are negotiating.

Of the ABMs we have developed for citation analysis, SASCA-ReSA is the most complex on account of adding authors as a model feature. This added feature comes with a computational cost, a five-fold performance penalty compared to SASCA-ReS. While SASCA-ReS can generate networks in the order of a at least 200 million nodes, this performance penalty restricts the scale of SASCA-ReSA both in terms of runtime and the size of the resultant network. This impacts our ability to explore SASCA-ReS and SASCA-ReSA together across a broad range of network sizes to examine converging and diverging trends across models. Accordingly, an ongoing task is to optimize performance from a systems perspective. Another direction being explored is to incorporate large language models (LLMs) in target selection.

In an environment where the demand for research resources exceeds its supply, where peer approbation is an ingredient of success, and where scientists are

judged by quantitative metrics, citation counts can be viewed as all-important. One adaptive response to such pressure is the manipulation of citations by cartels. Our simple representations of cartel behavior suggest a limited advantage to cartel membership. This advantage may be seen as useful by some. However, our observations were made under restrictive assumptions and do not explain more dramatic cartel effects such as those reported in the field of mathematics [7]. A complication in detecting cartels is that insular research communities may also display cartel-like behavior. Thus, distinguishing between cartels and insularity remains challenging. Furthermore, beyond growing in number and size, it is very likely that cartels exhibit greater sophistication in their activities than those depicted in our model, therefore an improved modeling of cartel behavior is needed.

We have previously posited the idea of a zero-sum game resulting from a system level “citation budget” at a point in time [8]. This framing implies that every citation gained by one article is a citation lost by another one. In our ABM simulations, this is true. Similarly, it is possible to envision a citation budget around a topic in the real world. Thus, while the gains made by cartel members might be small, transient, and accompanied by the risk of reputational loss, the coordinated strategies of cartels cause an unfair redistribution of citations that may be difficult to detect in the background of a larger network. To examine this redistribution carefully, the cartel experiments need to be redesigned to allow better measurement of their effects on non-cartel members and populations. Finally, a unifying theory of citation that plausibly accounts for motivations and can also be reconciled with quantitative observations is a matter of interest and investigation.

4 Methods

4.1 Data

Input data used for the experiments such as the seed set, recency distribution, out-degree distribution, and number of authors distribution are available at [26].

4.2 Model

We first provide a brief overview of SASCA-ReS and then present SASCA-ReSA, which builds on SASCA-ReS.

SASCA-ReS is an agent-based simulator that generates a citation network. In each time-step (year), new agents are created that cite other nodes in the network. Each node v in the network has attributes, which are its fitness, publication year, and in-degree; of these, only in-degree can change over time. We denote these by $\text{fitness}(v)$, $\text{year}(v)$, and $\text{in_degree}(v)$. An agent in SASCA-ReS is generated by random selection of another node in the network, which is termed the generator for the agent. When an agent A is created, it is assigned a quota of references to make, a value for α , and a phenotype, which provides values in

$[0, 1]$ for pa_w , and fit_w . The value for pa_w and fit_w are the relative weights given to preferential attachment and fitness, which are attributes of a given node (publication) in the network; hence $pa_w + fit_w = 1$ is enforced. The value for α determines the target fraction of the agent’s quota of citations that go to the 1-hop neighborhood of its generator. Therefore, α is independent of pa_w and fit_w .

Every agent cites its generator. With a small probability defined by the model, an agent may also cite a paper from the same year and a small percentage of its citation quota is reserved for fully random citations to nodes outside of the 2-hop neighborhood of the generator. After these, the agent makes citations to fulfill the remainder of its quota. The value for α specifies the target fraction of the remaining quota that is made to the 1-hop neighborhood of the agent’s generator, hence $1 - \alpha$ specifies the target fraction of the remaining quota that is made to the nodes that are distance 2 away from the generator.

Once the number of citations to be made to both distance-1 and distance-2 neighborhoods of the generator is determined, the agents in each neighborhood are first sampled to get a set of at most 10,000 nodes. These nodes are then binned by their publication year, and the agent allocates its citations to different publication year bins in order to fit a user-provided recency distribution [27]. Once the set of nodes to cite, defined by the publication year bins and the number of citations within each bin, has been determined, each node is then scored. When an agent scores a given node v , a node attribute score is computed first for each node attribute (fitness and in-degree), and then these attribute scores are weighted and summed, as we now describe.

We provide the preferential attachment score of node v (denoted by $pa_s(v)$) and the fitness score of node v (denoted by $fit_s(v)$) in Equation 1:

$$pa_s(v) = \frac{\mathbf{in_degree}(v)^\gamma + 1}{\sum_{x \in V} (\mathbf{in_degree}(x)^\gamma + 1)} \quad \text{and} \quad fit_s(v) = \frac{\mathbf{fitness}(v)^\gamma + 1}{\sum_{x \in V} (\mathbf{fitness}(x)^\gamma + 1)} \quad (1)$$

The score assigned to node v by the agent can be written as the weighted sum of these two scores, and is given in Equation 2.

$$\mathbf{score}(v) = pa_w \cdot pa_s(v) + fit_w \cdot fit_s(v) \quad (2)$$

Note that $pa_w + fit_w = 1$ and both $pa_s(v)$ and $fit_s(v)$ are normalized to sum up to 1 over all nodes in the candidate set (which is a subset of the nodes in the network). Hence the scores over all nodes in the candidate set naturally add up to 1, which means they can be interpreted as probabilities of being selected.

SASCA-ReSA extends SASCA-ReS through the inclusion of author features. The code for SASCA-ReSA is available at [25]. It includes as node attributes: number of authors (na) of each article and the reputation (ar) of the corresponding author. The reputation of an author is computed using the in-graph H-index. The number of authors per paper is based on a randomly assigned number, taken from a user-specified distribution. Correspondingly, the agents also

have two additional elements in their phenotype: ar_w and na_w . We require $pa_w + fit_w + ar_w + na_w = 1$. Hence, the scoring formula becomes

$$\text{score}(v) = pa_w \cdot pa_s(v) + fit_w \cdot fit_s(v) + ar_w \cdot ar_s(v) + na_w \cdot na_s(v) \quad (3)$$

Each publication at the time of creation is assigned a single author ID. The decision to either assign an existing author ID to this new publication or create a new author ID is made in order to come as close as we can to the distribution given by Lotka's law [22], which states that the number of authors with k articles (n_k) is roughly equal to $\frac{n_1}{k^2}$. However, only those authors whose first publication within the last 30 years are eligible to publish another publication.

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Contributions

All authors reviewed the manuscript before submission. MP developed the SASCA-ReSA implementation. TW, and GC planned the experiment(s). MP and GC analysed results. HY and IC developed code and generated data for the community search experiments. MP, TW, and GC interpreted the results of experiments, wrote and edited the manuscript.

Version Note

This third version of the manuscript features an additional figure pertaining to the cartel section. Fig 6 now reports annual citation rates, while Fig 7 reports cumulative citation rates. Other edits relate to improving readability and correcting minor typographic errors.

Additional information

4.3 Use of Artificial Intelligence

The authors declare the interactive use of assistive AI [1] for generating scripts for SLURM submissions, to aggregate results, and to generate figures. The text of the manuscript was written by the authors who acknowledge full responsibility for the content and conclusions presented. All the authors read and approved the manuscript.

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